

Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray and Thereafter*

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I consider it a great privilege to be invited to deliver the twentyfirst Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray Memorial Lecture and I thank the Council of the Indian Chemical Society for offering me this opportunity to pay my homage to the great savant on this auspicious day.

At the outset I may remind you about the little, instructive story on the description of an elephant by various persons, all eye-witnesses, having firsthand information—as a huge snake, pillar or winnowing fan depending on the particular portion of the body seen by the person concerned. The moral is that it is difficult to describe greatness and to have a proper picture about greatness it is necessary to put all the different *views* together, and I can just place before you the picture of Acharya Ray as I saw from some distance though staying practically by his side.

Unlike all my illustrious predecessors, I did not have any occasion to come in direct touch with Acharya Ray, although I spent a good number of years in the Chemistry Department of the University College of Science, Calcutta during the last part of his life. Often I saw this venerable, fragile man moving around in the corridor or chatting with people near the library of the Chemistry Department, where he was living in those days. But never did I venture to go in front of him or talk with him under any pretext. I heard many of his speeches and attended Prafulla Jayanti celebrations on his seventieth birthday.

Nevertheless, Acharya Ray was wellknown to me and I was greatly inspired by his selfless services from my early school days. While I was in class V of Keshub Academy, Calcutta, in one of my text-books there was an article presenting a vivid account of how in 1913 with the help of students, Acharya Ray personally carried out relief work in one of the great Damodar floods. The same year, *i.e.*, 1927, there was a similar flood, and myself and my class-mates were so much impressed by the above account of the relief work of Acharya Ray that we, at that tender age, formed into a group and started street collection after our class everyday for about a fortnight by singing from door to door. We had a fascinating experience as we were received with great affection and immense consideration wherever we went and had an excellent response from all classes of people. The collections were all sent to Acharya Ray, long before he started his famous *Sankattran Samity*.

As referred to by Professor S. R. Palit at the nineteenth Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray Memorial Lecture, Acharya Ray was very much against drinking of tea. When the British tea planters were trying to popularise tea in the country by making arrangements for free drinks, he raised a very effective slogan—চা পান না বিষ পান—meaning “drinking tea

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is drinking poison.” My father was a scholar in Sanskrit by birth and tradition. In those days, students of the Sanskrit College, Calcutta had to attend some classes in the Presidency College, and my father came in direct touch with Acharya Ray in the Chemistry class and with Acharya Jagadish Chandra Bose in the Physics class and he, in his turn, inspired me in science by telling tales about both of them.

As a true disciple of Acharya Ray, he did not allow drinking of tea in the family. As late as 1945, when I was in Oxford as a gentleman-at-large, my mother was very much worried for me for want of milk there in view of the rigors of rationing. I informed her in a letter that I managed with the landlady for having a cup of milk (of course diluted with hot water—like tea) at breakfast and another cup at dinner everyday. My father took it otherwise and thought that I was avoiding tea in view of the preachings of Acharya Ray and so he wrote back stating ‘You may take tea as it is very cold there.’

During my M.Sc. at the University College of Science, I started research work under Dr. J. C. Bardhan, just after his appointment as a Lecturer there. It was mostly from him that I came to know about the great contribution of Acharya Ray for the cause of Chemistry in this country. In his laboratory shelves I could see numerous bound volumes of the publications by Acharya Ray and these I was advised to go through in my spare time as a must. From him I often heard numerous fascinating stories regarding this great man. And from him I often heard how Acharya Ray advised him saying ‘A chemist should have the patience of an ass’ and ‘Hand is the best spatula’. His fervent expression clearly showed, on such occasions, that he was not merely preaching the doctrines of Acharya Ray but that he was a strong believer of those. He gave ample proof of his patience throughout his life. Just a few weeks prior to his retirement as the Khaira Professor and Head of the Department of Chemistry I saw him, on a Sunday, working alone in his laboratory using his hand as a spatula while filtering something at the water-pump. Once, while answering a delicate question from me he said, ‘They do not know how much I am indebted to Acharya Ray. All my inspiration for a research career is from this great *Gurudev*. And above all, how can I forget that I was the first recipient of the Nagarjuna Prize and the first to be awarded the Sir P. C. Ray Research Fellowship, both endowed by Acharya Ray to the Calcutta University from his life’s savings as a wage-earner’. I may point out that he carried out the famous Bardhan-Sengupta synthesis of phenanthrenes during the tenure of the above Fellowship and naturally Acharya Ray was very happy about it.

Old epics of various countries are said to run more or less parallel specially with regard to the various characters. One reason might be that the author had the same objective of placing before the contemporary public some ideal characters in a proper setting, no matter whether the author was a Grecian or an Indian. But the character of Ekalabya as an ideal disciple as painted by Vyasdev in the great Indian epic, the Mahabharata, is really unique and without a parallel. A great *Gurudev* like Dronacharya was great not merely because he had a large band of very good disciples of the normal type but also because he was very seriously worshipped as a *Gurudev* by one like Ekalabya without the knowledge of anybody. In this respect Acharya Ray had considerable resemblance to the great Dronacharya.

Dr. Aghore Nath Chattopadhyay had his D.Sc. of Edinburgh as early as 1875, and he was the first Indian to have this distinction. Acharya Ray had his D.Sc. of the same University fourteen years later, but shortly after his arrival in India, there dawned a new era in the country with regard to developments in Chemistry. Prior to him, chemical activity in this country was of a sporadic type. This included analysis of mineral water in 1833 by J. Prinsep of Geological Survey of India, Calcutta; preparation of Strychnine in 1833 by J. T. Pearson; studies on efflorescence of sodium sulphate of Tirhut in 1834 by J. Stephenson; chemical and physiological examination of Indian herbs and drugs as published in 1840 in 'Bengal Pharmacopoeia' and studies on arsenical poisons and the effect of sea water on iron in 1843 by W. B. O'Shaughnessy of Medical College, Calcutta; separation of mercury from gold and silver by distillation in 1852 by H. Piddington at Calcutta; determination of monthly changes in the quantity of suspended silt in Ganges water at Calcutta in 1854 and of chemical nature of paraffins obtained from Burma in 1860 by D'Waldie; test for porphyroxin in Indian opium in 1867 by Dr. Kanai Lal Dey; analysis of coal gas and water supplies of Calcutta in 1875 by Sir Alexander Pedlar and Chandra Bhusan Bhaduri at the Presidency College, Calcutta and publication of a paper on cobra venom in the Proceedings of the Royal Society, London, by Pedlar and Pulin Behari Soor as also their work on the effect of light on chemical changes.

Shortly after his return from Edinburgh in 1889, Acharya Ray started on his pioneering project of building up a solid foundation for chemical research in this country by providing a band of research workers who were later recognised as top men in the various branches of chemistry. His able leadership inspired the growth of other centres of chemical activity in the country. He organised postgraduate teaching and research in chemistry at the University College of Science, Calcutta on a sound footing, stressed the need for chemical industries in the country, as exemplified through starting of the Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works Ltd., and lastly but not the least he founded the Indian Chemical Society. All these are basic requirements of a country in the field of Chemistry. Many of my predecessors have dealt in detail on these aspects and an excellent account of these has been published in 1966 by one of his illustrious students, Professor Priyadarajan Rây in the Biographical Memoirs of Fellows of the National Institute of Sciences of India, Volume I.

Since independence, more and more money is being made available for teaching and research in chemistry and numerous chemical industries have sprung up in the country along with numerous Universities and Research Institutes. It may be said that the country is throbbing with immense chemical activity as compared to the old days. There is good hope for more and more expansion in all the diverse activities. It is, however, high time for taking proper stock of the situation in the interest of properly regulating further growth before it is too late. In this respect I would like to take this opportunity of placing my views on some of the items of vital interest.

APPLIED RESEARCH

In a developing country like India, scientists should not remain secluded in their 'ivory towers', but this appears to be just a pious wish. As enormous encouragement and appreciation are available for pure research, even a scientist engaged specifically for applied

research finds out ways and means for carrying out pure research. And if there is a case of even such a scientist having a *national recognition*, one may well imagine the consequent aspirations of his enterprising followers. It is better to start using the term 'pure' in place of loose use of such high sounding terms as 'basic' or 'fundamental'. It is not difficult for a senior worker to win fame and for a junior worker to achieve his doctorate through pure research. In the interest of the country, these should be *made easier* through applied research. As it stands, pure research is progressing at a great premium in this country. At the time of a serious emergency, however, the unfavourable effects of the more favourable conditions for pure research become evident.

RESEARCH IN THE INDUSTRIES

In the more progressive countries, applied research forms a vital item for most of the industries. On the other hand, the contribution of the Indian industries to research leaves much to be desired of. There should be much better scope for collaboration between scientists attached to the research institutions and the industries instead of the industries depending solely on foreign blue prints all the time. Had he been living, Acharya Ray would have been sore about the present state of affairs. We shout so much for Indianisation but at heart we still like to depend on the foreigners.

CENTRAL SERVICE LABORATORIES

Although it has been possible to establish a large number of well-equipped research laboratories in the country, chemists working in less privileged laboratories are still having difficulties even for such petty analyses as micro, C, H, N. Pre-purchase declarations for helping other scientists while making out a case for sanction of necessary grant and foreign exchange for procuring a costly equipment by a privileged institute often becomes inoperative after having the equipment. A well-equipped Central Service Laboratory in each of the metropolis of scientific research in the country like Bombay, Calcutta, Delhi and Madras is a vital need for helping the research chemists in the respective zones. These may be run by the Government on a semi-commercial basis so that the service may be available at a subsidised rate. Whenever possible each such laboratory, should be provided with more than one equipment or set up of a single type, not only for meeting the demand but also for continuance of the service even when one is out of order. These Laboratories should be primarily meant for service, and researches, if any, should concern improvements of service. It may become more convenient even for the better privileged C.S.I.R./A.E.E. scientists to utilise these Laboratories, as in a specialised Service Laboratory it is much easier to keep the various equipments running regularly while catering for the needs of a large number of research institutes. In a research institute it is not unusual to find a big costly equipment lying idle as one corner installation merely as a show piece for the visitors. Regular continuity of the working of an equipment is the best means for proper maintenance of most equipments, particularly the modern electronic equipments. Wastage of money and valuable foreign exchange over purchase of such equipments by individual institutes including wastage due to keeping the equipments idle for want of sufficient pressure of work may be

avoided if the required services are available from the Central Service Laboratories. Facilities available from these Laboratories will be of immense help particularly to rising young workers working in less privileged institutes.

CENTRAL SCIENCE LIBRARIES

It is also necessary to have a Central Science Library in each of the above cities. These should contain all available books and journals in the various fields up-to-date and should be situated in the heart of the city.

THE BRAIN DRAIN

The 'brain drain', provided it is not really draining out of the brain matter, is not too much of a problem as compared to the host of others facing the country, and in any case India is not the only country suffering from this malady. For instance, even in Britain the position does not appear to be less acute. It is difficult to stop this if there is a greater demand for trained scientists in another country, and specially if the latter is able to offer greater emoluments. Importation of scientists is like a natural corollary to a country unable to train up the required number of scientists within the land. It is not at all proper to think that the 'brain drain' is a kind of discredit to India, just as it is not proper to discredit the scientist-absorbing country for her inability to produce the required number of scientists from amongst the sons of the soil utilising the training machinery available within the land. It may be noted that similar to international trade these are also to a considerable extent controlled by international policies.

In the pre-independence period there were few Universities and most of them had provision for D.Sc. only, which meant strenuous research work carried out independently for quite a long period and as such mostly good and tenacious workers could afford to try for it. During the tenure of the research work only the brightest students could secure a research scholarship. A few used to go to foreign countries for further training, a fraction of them being supported by State Scholarships. Even Loan Scholarships, maintained by charitable endowments, were meant for really top-ranking scholars in those days. After independence, the picture has changed completely. The number of Universities in the country is going up quite fast. In all these Universities there is now provision for Ph.D./D.Phil. for which one has to work under the guidance of a teacher. As compared to Western Universities, the conditions controlling the doctorate have been much simplified—it is not necessary to be a regular student of the University as the candidate can work in any laboratory even outside the jurisdiction of the University as a part-time worker with this provision that his teacher has the necessary recognition from the University. Whatever may be the reason, the standard of the doctorate, as at present, leaves much to be desired of. This may be evident from an average case. It is true that for Ph.D. there is a *viva voce* examination also, but failure in doctorate just on the basis of *viva voce* is a rare phenomenon. For Ph.D. it is better to adopt the American system of having advanced courses along with the cumulative examinations and the students should work in the University laboratories. This may even do away with the necessity for the M.Sc. Under the present conditions there is really

no need for D.Sc., but if it is continued, it should be allowed only after Ph.D. In a University where after M.Sc. one can try either for Ph.D. or for D.Sc., some of the Ph.D.s are found to be much better than post-independence D.Sc.'s.

P O O L O F F I C E R S

It is no doubt useful for young doctorates to go abroad and have firsthand information regarding research laboratories in the progressive countries of the West for broadening their outlook. In the preindependence days, the few going abroad were quite critical about selection of the foreign teacher/collaborator, but young scientists of to-day while going abroad have very little to choose in this respect in view of other considerations. The very outlook and approach of the two groups appear to be quite different. The real difficulty arises when they come back these days. In most instances they are not satisfied with the emoluments offered and also often think ill of the research facilities here.

The Government through the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research has made an honest attempt through the 'Scientists Pool' for the rehabilitation of these foreign-trained workers in this country. The object of the sponsors of the scheme is to provide such people with a tolerable platform immediately on landing in this country so that they may do something while trying for a job. In this respect, however, the scheme does not appear to be a successful one. It is not unusual to find the Pool Officers saying that they are not being treated fairly by the authorities of their laboratories. It is also not unusual to find that in the opinion of the other side such workers are not interested in research work and use their time otherwise. Perhaps it is better to provide for more specific duties for the Pool Officers, but the best thing would be to have a Pool Officers' Research Institute somewhere in India. With an experienced Emeritus Scientist at the helm and the ever-moving Pool Officers as the inmates, such an Institute may be able to reasonably compete with other research institutes in carrying out important collaborative projects specially in view of the freshly acquired experiences of the Pool Officers.

Under more or less similar circumstances, with the financial support of the Government, a Scientists Appointment Service has just been started in Britain, which is being run jointly by the Royal Institute of Chemistry, the Institute of Biology, the Institute of Physics and the Physical Society, the Institute of Mathematics and its Applications, and the Institution of Metallurgists. British scientists taking up postdoctoral fellowships abroad, who intend after this to return to proper employment in Britain, may have necessary connection with their prospective employers by taking advantage of this service so that they may be employed immediately after their return. A similar service may also be organised in this country.

I N D E P E N D E N T R E S E A R C H

Independent research is mainly in the interest of the individual scientist concerned and not so much in the interest of the country. If some work is good for the country, it is immaterial whether it is the work of one or more. In view of the great interest shown to this

item during selections, promotions, etc., a young scientist is indirectly encouraged to find out ways and means of carrying out independent research. This tendency is often the cause of various troubles in research laboratories. On the other hand, in the progressive countries of the West team work is the usual motto. A single scientist may do a little thing but if the cooperation of others are pulled together, better work is possible and there is better chance for training up others. Such a system is obviously much better in the general interest of the country.

INDIAN CADRE OF SCIENTISTS

It would be extremely advantageous to start an Indian Cadre of Scientists so that the Centre, the States, the Universities, the various research institutes and other public bodies may draw their requirements of scientists from this Cadre. It would no doubt be a big affair but it would solve numerous problems. Research offers the safest corner for under-activity and even inactivity, and this is gradually becoming a problem in our country. Sometimes a scientist finds it difficult to pull on with the authorities or loses interest in research for various reasons. In many instances, one appointed in an institute for applied research gets interested in pure research. It is no use compelling a scientist to do a job against his will, and all such cases can be tactfully tackled through transfers. A scientist may become more active in a changed environment and so also is one who has lost interest in research, specially when they are put in charge of routine jobs of the appropriate type. One who prefers pure research, though posted in an institute for applied research, may be transferred to a University so that he may have teaching also side by side, which is helpful for pure research. It is also extremely important to safeguard the interests of a young scientist from the personal likes and dislikes of his boss. It is no less important to remember that if a scientist is put in charge of a laboratory none of its constituents should be imposed on him against his will, as otherwise the head cannot be held responsible for the activities of the laboratory. Under the Indian Cadre of Scientists such problems can also be solved without much difficulty.

As at present, selection of a scientist for a particular post consumes a good portion of our resources, specially for the top-ranking posts. Sometimes it becomes very much time-consuming requiring several years, with consequent deterioration of the conditions of the laboratory. Such selections would become quite simple in a properly organised and managed Cadre of Scientists. In such a case, any wrong selection for a vacant post may be smoothly rectified by another transfer. On the other hand, as it stands at present, it is often extremely difficult to rectify the position created by a selection of the wrong person for a particular post except by short-circuiting him.

SCIENCE POLICY

It is extremely important in the interest of further development of the country along right lines, to appoint a Science Policy Commission for evolving a proper Science Policy after a thorough investigation of the prevailing conditions and requirements. From time to

time we hear an unkind criticism that scientists are not doing what they should have done. Once at an important meeting a speaker, occupying a very responsible position, criticised scientists in general saying that they are not doing anything for the country's defence. However, when the speaker was asked to produce the 'shopping list' for the defence, he could not produce any. The 'shopping list' is a very important item, and I feel that each of the research grant giving machineries of the country should formulate their respective lists and use a substantial portion of their funds in supporting research work on items from this list. At the same time, in very selected cases substantial research grants may be allotted to *rising young scientists*, preferably below the age of forty, without strings. With the growth of scientific activity, maintenance of proper ethics would become quite a problem, Acharya Ray was a strict disciplinarian and maintained a high standard of ethics amongst his students. It was one of his illustrious students, Professor J. N. Mukherjee, who placed the problem threadbare at a meeting of the Council of the Indian Science Congress Association at Cuttack in 1962. The appointment of a high-powered Censoring Committee is a dire need and is long overdue.

In one respect the position of this country may be described as very much satisfactory. This is with regard to the output : expenditure ratio for scientific research. It would be quite interesting and helpful, specially in a developing country like that of ours, to find out this ratio for the various research laboratories and institutes.

Lastly, I earnestly feel that the Government should pay more and more attention to the opinion of learned societies like the Indian Chemical Society in related important matters instead of solely depending on a few selected advisers to the Government in their strictly individual capacities. It is also necessary for the Government to look after the welfare of these bodies so that these may smoothly function and discharge their duties properly.